

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE STRATIGRAPHIC LAYER IN TOPONYMICS

Komila Shoyimova

Termez University of Economics and sevis

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13960257>

Annotation Despite its autonomous formation, the science of toponymy has engaged with many other topics throughout its evolution, and this interaction is still occurring on now. because toponyms are examined from a variety of angles by several disciplines. The rules of their formation in the form of rare words are studied by philologists, the etymological aspects are studied by linguists, the period and conditions of toponym formation are studied by historians, and the characteristics of toponym formation in interaction with various customs and lifestyles are studied by ethnographers.

Key words: Toponymy, stratigraphic layer, science, research, toponymic zoning.

Introduction

The word stratigraphy is derived from the Latin "stratum," which means "I write." Numerous fields make use of stratigraphic and layer analysis. For instance, rocks in the science of geology investigate the links between rocks and lithological strata as well as the changes in their geographical distribution throughout time. Studying the location of rocks, irrespective of their genetic makeup, the circumstances surrounding their creation, the rules governing formation, and the primary age are the fundamental goals of stratigraphy. In archeology, it serves to determine the age of cultural strata, whether they lie in an inter-periodic order or vice versa. Additionally, there are chances to use the stratigraphic analysis approach to the study of toponymy. This is due to the fact that some inter-periodic strata, like rocks, are also thought to have established the characteristics of the genesis of toponymic terminology. It is feasible to examine toponyms, their composition, formation characteristics, and nomenclatorial rules in close relation to certain natural-historical and political-economic factors by researching the intergenerational characteristics of these strata conditions. The implementation of this process will be more reliable if it is carried out through the study of indirect scientific literature, written sources. However, it is not always possible to use the scientific literature to reveal the etymological content of ancient toponyms. Because the lack or non-availability of literature does not allow it. In this context, the importance of stratigraphic layer analysis is further enhanced.

The main findings and results

The country's toponymic terms' geographical analysis reveals that the older the toponyms, the less certain their etymology is, the more the core's structure has changed, and the content is only understandable by experts due to a variety of historical and social influences. As a result, the meaning of the earliest toponymic names in the Republic's area is either entirely abstract or covered by some rough assumptions.

There is a layer of Greek toponyms that have not left a lasting impression on our nation, but we can see from some historical sources that they have survived. Greek toponyms are documented in the scientific writings of Greek scholars who lived in BC. Based on their geographical perspectives, Greek scientists can be divided into two groups. The first group of scientists, which included Hecati Miletsky, Herodotus, and Aristotle, did not visit Central Asia during their lifetimes, so they did not see our nation, but they did record the toponyms of our homeland in their works. The second group of scholars, such as Arrian, Curtius Rufus, Onesicritus, Kallitsefan, Harens, marched through the territory of Uzbekistan as part of Alexander the Great's army and studied it, writing down the toponyms of our country in Greek, sometimes in Greek transcription. For example:

1. Alexandria Eskhata -means long, remote Alexandria. The fortress built by Alexander the Great around the present-day cities of Ahangaron and Bekabad has not been preserved in our time

.2. Pardigvi is a city on the banks of the Amu Darya near Termez, according to Hafizi Abro (15th century). It was founded by Alexander the Great and named Pardigvi. Pardigvi means "hotel" when translated from Greek into Uzbek. an additional layer of Persian languages. Distributed across the nation, particularly in Zarafshan, Kashkadarya, Surkhandarya, and partially in the Fergana Valley, the layer of toponyms made up of Persian stems is also significant in stratigraphy. Persian, or Persian E.I.R. in the state language, is a member of the Indo-European language family's southwestern branch of the Iranian language group. widely distributed in the Caucasus, Central Asian, Afghanistan, Pakistan, India, Iraq, B.A.A., and the United States.

In Afghanistan, Dari is the contemporary Persian-Tajik language. The Ilkhhat monuments of the Achaemenid dynasty, which date from the U1-U centuries BC, are genetically inherited by ancient Persian. Four additional letters that depict the sounds distinctive of the Persian language are added to the Arabic alphabet, which serves as the basis for the inscription. According to their

creation history, toponyms with Persian-specific cores therefore encompass the pre-Christian era as well as the present. In the republic's area, there are several toponyms that make up the Persian layer, such as Charvaq (Chorbog-four gardens), Sangzor (Sang-tash, an adjective indicating hard place, rocky place, rocky river), and Navruz (Nav-new, Roz-kun, new day). These toponyms collectively comprise a huge layer.

Turkish toponyms in layers. There are several thousand years of history behind the linguistic evolution of Uzbekistan. The earliest regional languages that have evolved in our nation include Turkic, Persian, Arabic, and Old Uzbek, according to documented sources. Sagdullaev, A. As a result, even the oldest toponyms are mostly found in the cores of both languages, and occasionally they are created in a hybrid form by combining old and new Tajik and Uzbek terms. Nur-Ota v.h., Zaro'tsoy-Zar-ot-soy. It is believed that these toponyms originated in prehistoric times. By contrast, Bukhara is younger than Nurata. Narshaxiy (1996). The name "Bukhara" was first used for this purpose in BC.

Syrdarya means "curved river" in the ancient Turkic language [E. Murzaev-1984, p. 235]. In the works of the Greek historian Ptolemy [90-168] the ethnonym aria is found. The Aryans are a people living in the lower reaches of the Syrdarya-Yaksart. The meaning of the concept of ariak is arida, which means the peoples living on the other side. [S.Sh.Komoliddinov-2006. P. 89]. This concept has a pure Turkic origin and is still used by the peoples living in the territories of Khorezm and Karakalpakstan. [A.Akhmedov-1987]. However, during the numerous military campaigns in Central Asia, including Uzbekistan, the Turkic language partially lost its status and developed again. This situation is reflected in the stratigraphic layer specific to toponymy. The largest category in the republic is the layer of toponyms in the Turkish language. The colloquial phrases of both ancient and present Turkic peoples and ethnic groups are the source of toponyms that belong to this stratum; in fact, words with a Turkic origin are common not only in our country but also in other places. In addition to Uzbekistan, the Russian Federation, China, Afghanistan, Iran, Tajikistan, India, Bulgaria, Romania, Ukraine, Germany, Cyprus, Macedonia, Albania, the APC, Saudi Arabia, Ukraine, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Turkmenistan, and Turkey all speak Turkic languages. Included in this category are over 25 languages.

There are instances when the rocks exhibit the written look of the graves, and the toponyms of the oldest Turkic core were produced in prehistoric periods. It is simpler to ascertain the meaning of geographical names with

Turkic origins based on their etymology, and we can observe that they are rather frequent.

A layer of toponyms consisting of a Slavic core. It is quite large as a separate or stratographic layer and was formed on the territory of Uzbekistan in the XIX-XX centuries. The process of emergence of place names in the Russian language in our republic took place in connection with the Russian occupation of Central Asia in the late XIX and early XX centuries. As a result, toponyms such as Bogarnoe, Ilich, Skobelev, Moscow, Leninabad, which were not specific to the spirituality of the native population, but rather young, based on the rules of another language, could not be stable for a long time.

CONCLUSION

After the independence of the Republic, toponyms began to be restored in the form of national values. It has been replaced by names that reflect the demand of the time, popularly simple, understandable to all. Ancient historical names have been restored. For example: Kirov district in Tashkent, former Yunusabad, Sovetabad-Nurabad in Samarkand region, etc. Toponyms praising or expressing independence are being formed throughout the country. For example: Tashkent has Mustaqillik Square, Istiqlol Palace, streets and villages named after Hürriyet.

References:

1. Murzaev E.M. Essays on toponymy. M. "Misl. 1974.
2. Ulugov N. Historical and linguistic study of hydronyms of the Uzbek language. T. "Fan". 2008.
3. Enazarov T.J. "Issues of nomenclature" T. UzMU. 2010.
4. Qoraev C. Toponymy. Publishing House of the National Society of Philosophers of Uzbekistan. T. 2006.
5. Gulomov P., Mirakmalov M.T. Toponymy and geographical terminology.
6. Gulyamov Ya. History of irrigation of Khorezm. T. "Fan". 1957.
7. Khasanov X. From the history of Central Asian place names. T. "Fan". 1965.
8. Khasanov X. The secret of geographical names. T. "Uzbekistan". 1985.
9. Nigmatov Theory of natural geography and geocology. Monograph-T.: Navruz, 2018. –220 p.
9. Rasulov A. History and analysis of "sustainable development" or "sustainable development" // TDPU scientific information. –T., 2018. –4 (17). B. 20-26.

POLAND

CURRENT APPROACHES AND NEW RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCES

International scientific-online conference

POLAND

10.Rasulov A. Indicators of sustainable development and problems of their practical application // Information of the Geographical Society of Uzbekistan. Volume 49 -Tashkent, 2017. -p. 12-15.

11.Rasulov A.B. On the role of environmental indicators in the sustainable development of regions // Geography in XXI acp: problems, development, prospects. Materials of the Republican scientific-practical conference. -Samarkand, 2017, -p.19-22.